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DELIVERABLE LEADER: Felipe Bastida (CSIC)

AUTHOR: Alfonso Vera (CEBAS-CSIC), José A. Siles (CEBAS-CSIC), María Patiño-García (CEBAS-CSIC), Cristina Aponte (INIA-CSIC), Stefano Mocali (CREA), Ángeles Prieto-Fernández (MBG-CSIC), Beatriz Rodríguez-Garrido (MBG-CSIC), Carmen Trasar-Cepeda (MBG-CSIC) and Felipe Bastida (CEBAS-CSIC)

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ABSTRACT

This report explores how microbial communities from soils under different agricultural managements (different tillage intensity and fertilization) respond to drought. Microbial communities are essential for key soil ecosystem services, such as carbon sequestration and fertility, but their resilience to climate stressors like drought, particularly across different regions, is not well understood. The study focuses on long-term experiments (LTEs) from Switzerland, Spain, and France to examine whether consistent patterns emerge in how soil management influences microbial resilience to drought.

Soils subjected to organic and mineral fertilization and varying tillage intensities were incubated and exposed to intense drought conditions. Soil microbial biomass (EL-FAMES), activity (enzyme activities and basal soil respiration), and diversity and composition (DNA sequencing) were analyzed.

Key findings show that sustainably managed soils with organic fertilization and reduced tillage had higher bacterial biomass but were more sensitive to drought, especially in Swiss soils. Soil respiration increased after drought in most cases, while dehydrogenase activity decreased, and urease activity increased. Phosphatase and β -glucosidase activities decreased under drought conditions, with variations based on geographic location and soil management practices.

Analysis of microbial community composition revealed that bacterial communities were primarily shaped by agricultural management rather than drought, with the most noticeable changes observed in sustainably managed Swiss soils. However, fungal communities were more sensitive to drought effects, especially in French soils.

The study concludes that sustainable agricultural practices might enhance the resilience of microbial communities to drought by maintaining higher microbial biomass and activity. However, the effects of drought vary significantly depending on geographical location, with soils in different regions displaying distinct responses to drought stress. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of site-specific management strategies to improve microbial resilience and sustain soil health under changing climate conditions.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

EL-FAME.....Ester-linked fatty acid methyl ester

EU European Union

LTE Long-term experiment

MN-NT Mineral fertilization/non-tillage

MN-RT..... Mineral fertilization/reduced tillage

MN-NT Mineral fertilization/standard tillage

NMDS..... Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling

O-RTOrganic fertilization/reduced tillage

WHC..... Water holding capacity

WP Work Package

1. Introduction

Soil microbial communities are essential for driving soil ecosystem services, such as carbon sequestration and fertility. However, how different soil management practices, including fertilization type and tillage intensity, impact the resilience of these microbial communities to climate change is not well understood. This is particularly important on a large spatial scale, where soils host diverse microbial communities in varying environmental contexts, which can influence their resistance to climate stressors. In this study, we aim to understand how past agricultural management affects the resilience of soil microbial communities to intense drought. In many European regions, drought periods are expected to worsen. Therefore, predicting the ability of soil microbial communities to withstand such stress and understanding how agricultural management influences this capacity is crucial to selecting the most sustainable agricultural practices.

2. Material & methods

2.1. Experimental design

Soils from long-term experiments (LTEs) in Switzerland, Spain, and France (Task 3.1 of the EJP Soil Minotaur project) were chosen for their specific properties and microbial communities. This enables us to investigate whether there are consistent patterns in how agricultural practices influence the resilience of microbial communities to drought across different soils. For each LTE, soils with different types of fertilization (mineral vs organic) and tillage intensity were selected (Fig 2.1).

Figure 2.1. Picture of the various soil microcosm replicates placed in a growth chamber during incubation under controlled air humidity, temperature, and light conditions.

A soil incubation assay was conducted (Fig 2.1). Soils sieved to 2 mm were pre-incubated for 15 days at 80% of their water-holding capacity (WHC) (Time 0). This allowed the soils to adapt to local conditions after processing (sampling, sieving, shipping, storage, etc.). Subsequently, the soils were subjected to intense drought (no watering) for 45 days (Time 1) in greenhouse conditions until completely dried. Afterwards, soils were stored and analyzed, including enzyme activities and

indicators of microbial biomass (EL-FAMES). Further, soil DNA was extracted using the specified method, and the diversity and composition of bacterial communities (16S rRNA gene) and fungal communities (ITS2) were investigated.

Table 1. Experimental design of the microcosm incubation: Selected treatments and LTEs.

LTE	Treatment
ACO (France)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization/reduced tillage (O-RT) (×3 replicates) • Mineral fertilization/reduced tillage (MN-RT) (×3 replicates) • Mineral fertilization/standard tillage (MN-ST) (×3 replicates)
INIA (Spain)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization/reduced tillage (O-RT) (×3 replicates) • Mineral fertilization/non-tillage (MN-NT) (×3 replicates) • Mineral fertilization/reduced tillage (MN-RT) (×3 replicates) • Mineral fertilization/standard tillage (MN-ST) (×3 replicates)
Agroscope (Switzerland)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization/reduced tillage (O-RT) (×3 replicates) • Mineral fertilization/non-tillage (MN-NT) (×3 replicates) • Mineral fertilization/standard tillage (MN-ST) (×3 replicates)

2.2. Soil microbial biomass quantification

Contents of EL-FAMES in soil samples were measured according to the method described by Schutter and Dick (2000). Briefly, fatty acids were extracted from microbial cells and released as methyl esters by incubating 3 g of frozen soil with 15 mL 0.2 M methanolic KOH for 1 h at 37°C under periodic shaking. Afterwards, samples underwent pH neutralization with 1 M acetic acid. EL-FAMES were then partitioned into an organic phase by adding 10 mL hexane and vigorous shaking, followed by centrifugation and evaporation of the hexane in a SpeedVac (Labogene). EL-FAMES were finally resuspended in iso-octane and analyzed with an Agilent 8860 gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID), using a DB-FastFAME capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm ID × 0.25 μm film) (Agilent Technologies), with helium as the carrier gas. The chromatographic conditions were as follows: (i) an initial temperature of 80 °C for 1.5 min, (ii) an increase to 160 °C with a ramp of 40°C min⁻¹, (iii) then to 167°C at 0.5°C min⁻¹, (iv) then to 200°C at 30°C min⁻¹, (v) and finally to 230°C at 4°C min⁻¹. Henicosanoic (21:0) methyl ester was used as an internal standard. Fatty acids were identified according to their retention times and their absolute amounts in each sample (nmol g⁻¹ dry-weight soil) were calculated using commercially available fatty acid methyl ester and bacterial fatty acid methyl ester mixes (Sigma-Aldrich).

Each fatty acid was named according to the following format: total number of C atoms:number of double bonds, followed by additional information about the position of the terminal double bond (ω). Other notations are “Me” for methyl, “cy” for cyclopropane, the prefixes “i” and “a” for iso- and anteiso-branched fatty acids, respectively, and the suffixes “c” and “t” for -cis and -trans configurations, respectively. The fatty acids i15:0, a15:0, i16:0, 16:1ω9c, 10Me16:0, i17:0, cy17:0, 10Me18:0, and cy19:0 were used as bacterial markers. The fatty acids 18:2ω6,9t and 18:2ω6,9c were used as fungal markers. The unspecific microbial fatty acids 14:0, 15:0, 16:0, 17:0, 18:0, and 20:0, along with the bacterial and fungal markers, were used to calculate the total microbial abundance (Joergensen, 2022).

2.3. Soil enzyme activities

The activity of several enzymes was measured according to the following protocol. Briefly, the enzymes studied included β -glucosidase, urease, acid and alkaline phosphomonoesterase, arylsulphatase, and dehydrogenase, an oxidoreductase used as a marker for microbial metabolic activity. These enzymes were measured at their optimal pH levels, determined by testing activity across different pH values for each soil sample.

Acid and alkaline phosphomonoesterase, β -glucosidase, and arylsulphatase activities were quantified using substrates containing p-nitrophenyl moieties, with p-nitrophenol release measured spectrophotometrically at 400 nm. Specific methods followed include those of Tabatabai and Bremner (1969, 1970) for phosphomonoesterase, Eivazi and Tabatabai (1988) for β -glucosidase, and Trasar-Cepeda et al. (1985) for arylsulphatase.

Urease activity was determined following Nannipieri *et al.* (1980) by incubating soil with urea and measuring the ammonium (NH_4^+) released using an ammonia electrode. For dehydrogenase, activity was measured using idonitrotetrazolium violet (INT) as a substrate, with idonitrotetrazolium formazan (INTF) production quantified at 490 nm, as described by Camiña et al. (1998).

To ensure accuracy, enzyme activities were calibrated against standard curves for p-nitrophenol and INTF, and tests were conducted to verify that soils did not retain these products. In cases of product retention, calibration curves were prepared by incubating standards with the soil samples under the same conditions. Enzyme activities were expressed as μmol of product (p-nitrophenol or INTF) released per gram of soil per hour ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$).

All reported values represent the averages of duplicate measurements on triplicate soil samples, expressed on an oven-dried basis at 105°C. This approach ensured that the data reflected enzyme activity across different moisture conditions while maintaining comparability between the treatments at each LTE.

2.4. Basal soil respiration measurement

Soil basal respiration ($\text{mg CO}_2\text{-C kg}^{-1} \text{soil day}^{-1}$) was measured by placing 20 g of sample, at 50 % of its water holding capacity, in hermetically sealed flasks and incubating for 25 days at 28 °C in darkness. The CO_2 released was measured periodically (every day for the first 4 days and then weekly) with an infrared CO_2 analyzer (CheckMate 302 (Zr) CO_2 -100 %; MOCON Europe A/S, Ringsted, Denmark).

2.5. DNA extraction.

Total DNA was extracted from 250 mg of soil using the Dneasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (QIAGEN). Amplicon sequencing of bacteria (16S rRNA gene) and fungal communities (ITS) and bioinformatic procedures were performed according to García-Díaz *et al.* 2024.

3. Results

3.1. Microbial fatty acids

Figure 3.1. Ester-linked Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (EL-FAMES) content in soil (nmol g⁻¹ soil): total, bacteria, and fungi groups in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs. O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage. Capital letters indicate statistical significance between times (Time 0 and 1), while lowercase letters indicate statistical significance among soil management practices. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean (3 replicates).

Overall, soils subjected to more sustainable management (i.e. organic management with reduced tillage) showed higher contents of bacterial and fungal fatty acids (Fig. 3.1). In the case of soils from France and Spain, bacterial biomass was not affected by drought in any management. However, bacterial biomass in Swiss soils decreased after drought in all managements, in the most sustainable management (organic with reduced tillage).

Fungal biomass was more sensitive to drought than bacteria. Overall, we found a decrease in the content of fungal fatty acid representatives in most of the soil management. This reduction was particularly evident in soils from France and Swiss, which seem sensitive to drought conditions. In the case of Switzerland soils, as in the case of bacteria, fungal biomass was more sensitive in soils organically managed with reduced tillage and in the less sustainable soil (mineral fertilization plus standard tillage). Regarding the fungal-to-bacterial biomass ratio, which is a simple indicator of changes in microbial community composition, most soils decreased this ratio after drought with the only exception of MN-ST in Switzerland which shows no difference (Fig. 3.2).

Figure 3.2. Soil fungi/bacteria ratio (from EL-FAME content) in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs (France, Spain, and Switzerland). O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage. Capital letters indicate statistical significance between times (Time 0 and 1), while lowercase letters indicate statistical significance among soil management practices. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean (3 replicates).

3.2. Basal respiration and enzyme activities

Figure 3.3. Soil basal respiration in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs. O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage. Capital letters indicate statistical significance between times (Time 0 and 1), while lowercase letters indicate statistical significance among soil management practices. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean (3 replicates).

Figure 3.4. Dehydrogenase activity in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs. O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage. Capital letters indicate statistical significance between times (Time 0 and 1), while lowercase letters indicate statistical significance among soil management practices. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean (3 replicates).

In comparison with microbial biomass, soil respiration increased after drought in most of the managements and sites (Fig. 3.3). France's soils experienced the most intense increase in soil respiration after drought, in comparison with soils in Spain and Switzerland. The only exception to this trend was the Spanish soil with mineral fertilization and standard tillage that showed a noticeable decrease in soil respiration after drought.

Figure 3.5. Urease activity in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs. O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage. Capital letters indicate statistical significance between times (Time 0 and 1), while lowercase letters indicate statistical significance among soil management practices. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean (3 replicates).

Contrarily to soil respiration, dehydrogenase activity decreased noticeably in all the soils after drought (Fig. 3.4). Patterns for soil enzyme activities were highly dependent on the type of enzyme, site and management. For instance, urease activity increased with drought in all the soils, this increase being the greatest in organically managed with reduced tillage soils in France and Switzerland (Fig. 3.5). The increase in urease activity with drought was also evident in all soils in Spain, but less intense than in France and Switzerland.

In the case of phosphatase and β -glucosidase activities (Fig. 3.6), drought decreased this activity, in all countries, but such decrease was most intense in France and Switzerland soils. In Spain, alkaline phosphatase activity was more resistant to drought in less sustainable managed soils (mineral fertilization plus standard tillage). In the case of arylsulphatase, the pattern depended on the country. In France and Spain, there was a trend to reduce or stabilize with drought, but in Switzerland, drought increased arylsulphatase activity, particularly in mineral-fertilized soils.

Figure 3.6. The activity of β -glucosidase, arylsulphatase and both acid and alkaline phosphomonoesterase enzymes in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs. O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage. Capital letters indicate statistical significance between times (Time 0 and 1), while lowercase letters indicate statistical significance among soil management practices. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean (3 replicates).

3.3. Microbial community composition

We explore the structure and composition of prokaryotic and fungal communities through 16S rRNA gene and ITS amplicon sequencing. For all the soils, the prokaryotic community was dominated by Actinobacteria and Proteobacteria. The relative abundance of Actinobacteria in Spanish soils was greater than in France and Switzerland. Switzerland soils had a greater abundance of Acidobacteria than the others (Fig. 3.7).

Figure 3.7. Bacterial community composition through 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs. O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage.

The fungal community was dominated by Ascomycota, followed by Basidiomycota and Mortierellomycota in all soils (Fig. 3.8). The relative abundance of Acomycota in Spanish soils was higher than that in French and Swiss ones. As in the case of the bacterial community, the structure of the fungal community differed with soil management. Drought exerted a notable influence on fungal community structure in French soils, but not in Swiss and Spanish ones.

Figure 3.8. Fungal community composition through ITS amplicon sequencing in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs. O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage.

The structure of both prokaryotic and fungal communities was mainly determined by the country, which was the most important factor in structuring communities (Fig. 3.9).

Figure 3.9. Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) ordination based on the Bray-Curtis similarities of both bacterial and fungal OTU communities in soils under different agricultural practices from three LTEs and at two different times (Time 0 and 1). O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage.

Figure 3.10. Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) ordination based on the Bray-Curtis similarities of bacterial communities per country. Two different times (Time 0 and 1). O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage.

Figure 3.11. Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) ordination based on the Bray-Curtis similarities of fungal communities per country. Two different times (Time 0 and 1). O-RT: organic fertilization + reduced tillage, MN-NT: mineral fertilization + non-tillage, MN-RT: mineral fertilization + reduced tillage, and MN-ST: mineral fertilization + standard tillage.

When splitting the results per country, we observed that the structure of bacterial communities, as studied by non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS), was mainly shaped by the type of management, rather than by drought (Fig. 3.10). Nevertheless, we could find some differences in the case of organic management with reduced tillage in Switzerland for which prokaryotic community structure after drought was different to that under optimal moisture conditions. In the case of the fungal communities, we observed that the fungal communities in French soils were more sensitive to the effects of drought than in Spanish and Swiss soils. (Fig. 3.11).

4. Conclusions

Our study highlighted key conclusions regarding the effects of soil management practices and drought on microbial biomass, activity, diversity and composition. Sustainable agricultural practices, such as those with organic practices and reduced tillage, showed higher bacterial and fungal fatty acids, indicating higher microbial biomass. Fungal biomass was more sensitive to drought than bacterial biomass; while levels remained stable in France and Spain, they declined in Swiss soils, particularly in sustainable systems.

After drought conditions, the F/B ratio typically decreased, except for one Swiss treatment (MN-ST). Soil respiration increased in most management types, particularly in France, while Spanish soils with mineral fertilization and standard tillage experienced a decline. The sensitivity of enzyme activities against drought across countries and managements varied with the type of enzyme activity.

Geographical location (country) rather than agricultural practices has played a key role in shaping the structure of the bacterial and fungal communities. Inside each LTE, soil management had a greater influence on bacterial communities than drought, especially in Switzerland (O-RT). For fungal communities, the French soils appeared to be more sensitive to drought effects than the soils from Spain and Switzerland.

Overall, these results highlight the importance of sustainable management practices for enhancing microbial resilience to drought and suggest the need for tailored soil management strategies that account for local environmental conditions.

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